

A PILOT CLINICAL STUDY TO EVALUATE THE EFFICACY AND SAFETY OF MAGNESIUM AND VITAMIN B6 SUSPENSION FOR THE TREATMENT OF MIGRAINE

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ABSTRACT

Background: *Migraine is a debilitating neurological disorder affecting approximately 12% of the global population, marked by severe headaches and associated symptoms. It contributes significantly to disability and is a significant component of the worldwide disease burden. Given its involvement in regulating serotonin function and vascular tone, Magnesium's role in migraine treatment has been investigated for its potential benefits in reducing migraine symptoms.*

Objective: *This pilot clinical study aimed to evaluate the efficacy and safety of Megrim suspension, containing magnesium and vitamin B6, for the treatment of migraine.*

Methodology: *In a 12-week, open-label, prospective pilot study, 50 patients aged 18-65 with migraine (with or without aura) were enrolled. Patients received 20 ml of Megrim suspension daily. Primary outcomes included mean migraine days, monthly migraine frequency, duration of daily migraines, severity (Visual Analog Scale), and Migraine Headache Index Score (MHIS). Secondary outcomes assessed the rate of recurrence and responder rate ($\geq 50\%$ reduction in migraine frequency).*

Results: *After three months, there was a significant reduction in migraine days (8.65 ± 2.24 vs 5.29 ± 1.95 , $P < 0.05$), headache duration (6.38 ± 2.35 to 4.88 ± 2.50 hours/day, $P < 0.001$), and severity (8.06 ± 1.53 vs 5.23 ± 1.72 , $P = 0.003$). The MHIS decreased significantly from 14.11 ± 6.24 to 7.70 ± 2.91 ($P < 0.001$). Eighty-eight percent of patients were classified as responders, further reinforcing the safety and efficacy of the treatment. The treatment was well tolerated, with mild gastrointestinal discomfort reported by seven patients.*

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Conclusion: *Megrim suspension significantly reduces migraine days, duration, severity, and overall migraine burden, demonstrating its efficacy and safety as a therapeutic option for migraine management. Further research with larger samples and longer follow-up is warranted to confirm these findings and assess long-term benefits.*

Keywords: Clinical Trial, Magnesium, Pyridoxine, Migraine Disorders

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1. INTRODUCTION

Migraine is a debilitating neurological condition characterized by recurrent, often severe headaches accompanied by neurological symptoms such as nausea, vomiting, and sensory hypersensitivity, affecting approximately 12% of the population. Migraine attacks are classified within the highest disability category by the WHO, contributing to 45.1 million years lived with disability (YLDs), which accounts for 5.6% of the global disease burden, surpassing all other neurological disorders combined. A 2019 age-period cohort analysis by Fan et al. revealed that the worldwide incidence of migraine had risen to 87.6 million (95% UI: 76.6, 98.7), marking a 40.1% increase since 1990, with India, China, the United States, and Indonesia together accounting for 43.6% of global cases.[1]

Migraine patients endure a significant disease-related burden, including disability, impaired performance at work and home, and interruptions to family and leisure activities. The burden extends beyond migraine episodes, with patients also experiencing interictal impairment. Migraine is associated with comorbidities such as depression, anxiety disorders, and sleep disorders like insomnia.[2] Current migraine management strategies include acute treatments like NSAIDs, triptans, and Calcitonin gene-related peptide (CGRP) antagonists to relieve symptoms during an attack. At the same time, preventive measures such as beta-blockers, antiepileptics, and lifestyle modifications aim to reduce the frequency and severity of migraines.[3]

Magnesium, an intracellular cation, has been linked to the regulation of serotonin function and vascular tone, mechanisms that suggest its role in migraine treatment.[4] Magnesium inhibits NMDA receptors and prevents calcium influx into cells. Research indicates that NMDA receptors are critical in the onset and progression of Cortical Spreading Depression (CSD), a phenomenon associated with migraine aura. Magnesium deficiency can induce CSD by disrupting mitochondria's oxidative phosphorylation and neuronal polarization. By counteracting vasospasm, inhibiting platelet aggregation, stabilizing cell membranes, and reducing the production of inflammatory mediators, magnesium may address various aspects of neurogenic inflammation during migraine. Several studies have demonstrated that migraine patients have lower serum magnesium levels compared to healthy individuals.[5]

Pyridoxine, a form of vitamin B, plays a crucial role in various metabolic processes and has been linked to improvements in vascular function related to migraine attacks. Research suggests that administering pyridoxine can lower homocysteine levels, which in turn may reduce the severity and frequency of headaches and alleviate migraine-related disability. Thus, pyridoxine supplementation could potentially enhance migraine symptoms by decreasing serum homocysteine concentrations.[6]

This pilot clinical study aims to evaluate the efficacy and safety of Megrim suspension for the treatment of migraine.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Study Design

The study was a 12-week, open-label, prospective, pilot clinical study. The protocol was approved by the Suraksha Ethics Committee, Mumbai. All patients had provided informed consent before enrolment in the study. The data was collected using a standardized case report form, including demographics, medical history, treatment duration, and details of concomitant medications.

2.2. Study Participants

Patients with an age range of 18-65, both male and female, were included in the study. Patients with migraine with or without aura diagnosed according to the IHS-criteria ICHD-II 1.1 and 1.2 were included. Patients with an age at onset of migraine less than 50 years and a diagnosis of migraine at least one year before initiation of the study were enrolled. Other inclusion criteria were three migraine attacks per month in the last three months before recruitment and not more than ten headache days, patients receiving routine treatment for managing migraine symptoms, and patients who did not participate in a similar investigation in the past four weeks.

Pregnant and lactating women, current smokers, and patients who used migraine prevention (drugs, nutritional supplements or psychotherapy) as well as antipsychotic or antidepressant medication during the last 3 months before study entry and throughout the study were excluded from the study. Treatments for other conditions which may affect migraine prevention were not allowed. These were mainly beta-blockers (e.g. propranolol, bisoprolol, metoprolol), calcium-antagonists (e.g. flunarizine), antiepileptics (e.g. topiramate, valproate), antidepressants (e.g. amitriptyline), supplements containing petasites (butterbur) or tanacetum (feverfew), magnesium or vitamin B6. Non-medical/non-nutritional treatment for migraine prevention like acupuncture or psychotherapy were also not permitted. (However, participants were allowed to treat migraine attacks with their usual rescue pain medication and anti-emetics). Patients with overuse of analgesics, tension-type headaches, patients with chronic kidney disease or metabolic disorders (diabetes and cardiovascular diseases), patients taking oral contraceptive drugs, patients who failed to respond to more than 2 different prophylactic agents in the past, patients resistant to all acute migraine drugs and patients who were unable to understand the procedures and protocol were also excluded from the study.

2.3. Study product

The study product was Megrim suspension (manufactured by Stabicon Life Sciences Pvt. Ltd), a combination of magnesium 325 mg and vitamin B6 (as pyridoxine HCl) 1.4 mg. The product was administered in a dose of 20 ml once daily for three months.

2.4. Outcome measures

The primary outcome measures included mean days with migraine, mean monthly migraine headache rate, mean duration of migraine headache per day, migraine severity using VAS score for pain and mean migraine headache index score (MHIS). A migraine day was defined as a day with at least 4 hours of pain or a day with pain and concomitant intake of pain medication. For each migraine day, the patient-rated pain intensity as mild, moderate or severe. MHIS was calculated as $MHIS = \text{duration (day)} \times \text{headache frequency} \times \text{headache severity}$. Secondary outcome measures included rate of recurrence; responder rate defined as the percentage of patients having $\geq 50\%$ reduction in migraine frequency from baseline after treatment with Megrim suspension. All the outcomes were measured at baseline and end of treatment.

2.5. Statistical analysis

A sample size of 50 was considered for the study. Descriptive statistics was used to present the data in mean \pm SD. A paired t-test and Wilcoxon Sign Ranked Test were used to measure significance.

3. RESULTS

A total of 80 patients were screened for eligibility; 50 patients who met the inclusion criteria were enrolled in the study, of whom 76% were women, with a mean age of 41.1 ± 10.6 years. All of them completed the study without any event of early withdrawal. Past medical history included migraine medication such as flunarizine, propranolol and amitriptyline. Their demographic and baseline clinical characteristics are summarized in Table 1. Most of the patients (70%) had migraine onset between 18-25 years of age.

Table 1: Patients' baseline and clinical characteristics

Variable	Study sample N=50 N (%)
Sex	
Males	12 (24%)
Female	38 (76%)
Age \pm SD	41.1 \pm 10.6 years
Height in cm \pm SD	158.4 \pm 7.8
Weight in kgr \pm SD	66.5 \pm 9.7
Age at migraine onset	
18-25 years	35 (70%)
25-40 years	7 (14%)
40-50 year	8 (16%)
Type of migraine	
Aura	12 (24%)
Non-Aura	38 (76%)

There was a significant reduction in days with migraine (8.65 ± 2.24 vs 5.29 ± 1.95 , $P < 0.05$) between baseline and end of treatment (Fig. 1). This effect remained significant in males and females ($P < 0.001$). Moreover, migraine severity was also significantly decreased as measured by the change in the number of monthly days with peak migraine intensity of more than four (moderate/severe pain) on a 0–10 numerical scale between baseline and end of treatment. (8.06 ± 1.53 vs 5.23 ± 1.72 , $P = 0.003$) (Fig. 2).

Figure 1: change in number of days with migraine

Figure 2: change in migraine severity

The duration of migraine headaches per day significantly reduced from 6.38 ± 2.35 to 4.88 ± 2.50 hours/day ($P < 0.001$) (Fig. 3). The beneficial effect of active supplementation regarding migraine severity and duration was evident in both types of migraine patients with aura and without aura ($P < 0.05$ for both). There was a significant reduction in MHIS from baseline to the end of 3 months (14.11 ± 6.24 to 7.70 ± 2.91 , $P < 0.001$) (Fig. 4).

Figure 3: change in duration of migraine

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Figure 4: change in migraine headache index score (MHIS)

Out of 50, 6 patients had a recurrence of headache (2 hours post-consuming the study drug) and required rescue pain medication (range 1-4 times). At the end of 3 months, 44/50 (88%) had experienced a $\geq 50\%$ reduction in mean migraine days and were therefore classified as responders. The remaining six patients (12%) reported less than 50% reduction with supplementation. Among the remaining non-responders, one patient experienced no benefit, while five patients (10% of the total study population) achieved less than a 30% reduction in mean migraine days.

Active supplementation also proved to be safe and well tolerated. Seven patients reported GI discomfort and diarrhea, which was mild in all cases and resolved without additional treatment. The patients were able to complete the study without discontinuing the study drug. No other adverse events were reported.

4. DISCUSSION

Migraine is a debilitating neurological condition characterized by severe headaches and associated symptoms. This study evaluated the efficacy and safety of Megrim suspension in treatment of migraine. The outcomes focused on mean migraine days, mean monthly migraine headache frequency, mean duration of migraine headaches per day, the severity of migraines assessed using the VAS for pain, and the mean MHIS. In our study, after three months of treatment, there was a significant reduction in migraine days (8.65 ± 2.24 vs 5.29 ± 1.95 , $P < 0.05$), and the duration of daily migraine headaches significantly decreased from 6.38 ± 2.35 to 4.88 ± 2.50 hours/day ($P < 0.001$). Additionally, migraine severity scores were notably reduced (8.06 ± 1.53 vs 5.23 ± 1.72 , $P = 0.003$), along with a significant decrease in MHIS (14.11 ± 6.24 to 7.70 ± 2.91 , $P < 0.001$).

Similarly, Gaul et al. demonstrated that treatment with a specialized supplement containing magnesium, riboflavin, and Q10 positively impacted migraine frequency.[7] Esfanjani et al. reported significant reductions in all migraine indicators with magnesium supplementation ($P < 0.05$).[8] Vikelis et al. found a reduction in the mean number of migraine days, peak headache intensity, and use of acute headache medications with magnesium combination supplementation.[9] A larger double-blind, placebo-controlled randomized trial involving 81 adult patients who met the International Headache Society (IHS) criteria for migraines also demonstrated notable improvements in those receiving magnesium treatment. The active magnesium group showed a significant reduction ($P < 0.05$) in the frequency of attacks.[10] In a study by Koseoglu et al., the prophylactic impact of daily oral magnesium supplementation was assessed in 30 patients suffering from migraines without aura. The results revealed a

notable reduction in migraine attack frequency and severity following magnesium treatment. Additionally, the P1 amplitude, measured through visual evoked potential examination, significantly decreased.[11]

A recent systematic review analyzing five randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trials in adult migraine patients indicated the benefits of daily magnesium dicitrate (600 mg) for migraine prevention. The review highlighted that magnesium supplementation was effective and well-tolerated, making it a cost-effective strategy for clinical practice.[12] In a similar clinical trial conducted by Lea and colleagues, the combined intake of pyridoxine, folate, and cobalamin was shown to reduce the severity and frequency of migraine attacks significantly and marked improvement in migraine-related disability. These findings suggest that supplementation with these vitamins may provide additional therapeutic benefits in managing migraines, potentially enhancing patients' overall quality of life by decreasing both the frequency and impact of migraine episodes.[13] Similarly, Villegas-Salas and colleagues conducted a randomized, triple-blinded, controlled trial to assess the effects of 150 mg pyridoxine supplementation on headache severity over 30 days. The study revealed a significant reduction in headache severity in the group receiving pyridoxine, indicating that this vitamin may have a beneficial role in alleviating headache symptoms in migraine patients.[14]

In summary, the findings from our study align with previous research demonstrating the efficacy of nutritional supplements, particularly magnesium, pyridoxine, folate, and cobalamin, in reducing migraine frequency, severity, and disability. The significant improvements observed in migraine days, duration, severity, and headache index scores with Megrim suspension further reinforce the potential of such therapies in migraine management. These results suggest that Megrim suspension, with its well-tolerated safety profile, can be used for migraine management. Long term data and real-world evidence in patients with comorbidities are needed.

5. CONCLUSION

This pilot study demonstrated that Megrim suspension is an effective and safe treatment for the management of migraines. Significant reductions in migraine days, headache duration, severity, and overall migraine burden were observed after three months of treatment, as reflected by the MHIS. Given its efficacy and favorable safety profile, Megrim suspension offers a promising therapeutic option for patients suffering from migraines, potentially improving their clinical outcomes and quality of life.

Conflicts of interest: Nil

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